

Prioritizing Railway Network Development Options from the Passenger Transportation Point of View; Case Study: I.R. Iran

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Abstract

the development of railway transportation network has been paid attention to in recent years because of some advantages over the other transportation ways such as lower fuel consumption, lower pollutant production, environmental protection, lower area occupation and higher safety levels. The construction of important lines such as Bafq- Bandar Abbas, Mashhad-Sarakhs, Ardakan- chadormalu, Bafq-Mashhad and two-way lines of Tehran-Qom and Tehran-Mashhad confirms are examples of the efforts for the railway network development.

In order to choose and propose a line to be constructed and provide technical and economic justification reports for the projects, usually the "freight transportation" is considered as the important factor in the calculations because of the higher economic gains and lower operational costs in comparison with the "passenger transportation." Besides this factor, there are some other important factors such as social and cultural development and reducing human fatalities. By considering these factors in spite of the cost as the design factors, it is possible to include the "passenger transportation" in the selection factors of proposing new lines for construction.

In this paper, by reviewing previous researches in the field of railway network development and gathering the most recent information about the development plans, the proposed plans for the development are presented. The criteria for comparison of the plans are chosen and prioritizing the plans is performed using "TOPSIS" decision analysis method with the "passenger transportation" approach.

Keywords: railway transportation, railway network development, MADM, TOPSIS

1. Introduction

1.1. Railway Network Transport

Transportation networks (especially railways) are the vital pillars of the economy and the connection of the society, which can relate all social, economic, military and agricultural clusters. Communication arteries carry the highest volume of goods and passengers with a relatively high confidence level to the intended destinations. Along with the network development, rail fleet technology has also achieved high-speed wagons for use in urban and inter-urban routes.

Nowadays, inter-city railways in developed countries compete well with air transportation in terms of price, speed, safety, and welfare and in the cities and suburbs, their safety, speed, capacity and services are the main and desirable options for the managers of large and developed cities.

Today, in many countries railways are being rebuilt and modernized. New lines (especially at high speeds) are under construction, and most of the old railroads are in the process of being restored.

The development of the rail transportation network, due to its competitive advantages over other transportation options such as saving fuel consumption, producing fewer pollutants and protecting the environment, occupying the minimum land, and also high safety, has always been considered as an important goal. The implementation of major rail projects such as Bafq-Bandar Abbas, Mashhad-Sarakhs, Ardakan-Chadormalu, Tehran-Qom, Tehran-Mashhad, and Bafq-Mashhad are examples of this effort for railway development in the I.R. Iran.

In order to select the proposed rail paths and, consequently, to prepare the technical and economic justifications for these options, the "freight section" is usually selected as the effective factor of calculation, since this segment has more outcome and less operating cost than the "passenger section." Irrespective of the financial dimension of the options, some other criteria such as the social and cultural development of the society and the reduction of human casualties could also be used to include the "passenger segment" in the process of making the decision for choosing new railways options.

1.2. Literature Review

Deciding in complex, unstable environments is one of the most important issues in modern management. In these cases, the decision maker is faced with different options under different criteria that affect the internal and external environment of the organization. Therefore, Multi - Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) models are considered as one of the most necessary tools in such conditions [1]. A typical decision making process includes eight steps which are shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 1 Flowchart of a typical decision making process [2]

All of the MCDM models are on the basis of a decision table. For a decision making problem with N criteria and M alternatives, the decision table is shown in

Table 1 schematic of decision table [3]

	A ₁	A ₂	...	A _n
C ₁	a ₁₁	a ₁₂	...	a _{1n}
C ₂	a ₂₁	a ₂₂	...	a _{2n}
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
C _m	a _{m1}	a _{m2}	...	a _{mn}

MCDM models are categorized into two main approaches: multi-attribute decision making (MADM) and multi-objective decision making (MODM) [4-6]. The desired goals and attributes are clear in MADM but are usually implicit in MODM. In contrast, the decision limitations are clearly defined in MODM. Because of the more fitness of MADM to decision problems in transportation issues, in this research MADM is considered as the basis of the analysis.

MADM models used in transport issues are divided into two categories of non-compensatory and compensatory models [7]. Non-compensatory models include methods in which the exchange between indices is not allowed (i.e., the weaknesses of an index are not offset by the existing advantage of another indicator) [8, 9].

Compensatory models include methods in which exchange is allowed among the indices. It means that a small change in an index can be offset by a reverse change in another index or other indices. This group of models can be divided into three sub-groups of concordance, compromising and scoring.

When the attribute data are available, the MADM methods can be divided into three groups of cardinal, ordinal and standard. The well-known methods of SMART, AHP, TOPSIS, ELECTREE, HRM, and WP are

of a cardinal type. In this research, the TOPSIS method is implemented for decision making. In the following, a brief review of this method is presented.

Figure 2 Subdivision of MADM compensatory methods based on data processing [7]

1.3. TOPSIS Model

This model, which is one of the best and simplest MADM models, was proposed by Huang and Yun in 1981[10]. This technique is based on the concept that the final result should have the least distance with the ideal solution (best possible condition) and the greatest distance with the anti-ideal solution (the worst possible condition). It is assumed that the desirability of each indicator is uniformly incremental or decreasing. The main steps of this method are as follows:

- Constructing the matrix of indices
- Non-dimensionalization
- Linear Nondimensionalization
- Determination of weight of the indices
- Constructing a non-dimensionalized weighted matrix
- Calculation of each option distance to the ideal and anti-ideal solution
- Prioritizing the options

2. Requirements of Railway Network Development

The effective factors are used to evaluate the proposed railway development options and compare them are as follows:

- Comparison of economic outcome and income of the proposed option (economic evaluation)
- The areas covered by the new option including freight poles such as ports, agricultural, mineral and industrial centers (especially heavy industries); population poles (centers of provinces and large cities); cultural, religious and historical centers
- A rail connection to ports, customs and railways of other countries in terms of facilitating international transportation and earning money through the transit of goods, as well as creating stability and security.

- High level of confidence about the amount of the load or passenger in the proposed option that reduces the risk.
- In areas where the road network has a desirable development, it is important to compete with the road in that region.
- Due to problems with the employment of human resources and the maintenance of the lines in less-favored areas, they have less privilege.
- Sometimes, political, military or social goals are effective in determining the priority of the options.

3. Prioritizing railway development options

As it was previously mentioned, in this paper the passenger transportation is considered for the railway development. The following criteria are defined for prioritizing the options:

- Travel demand (in terms of number and person - kilometer)
- The average cost of construction per kilometer in the path
- The competitive advantage of the route with the same road transport (safety, travel distance, shipping cost).
- Capability to cover important areas
- The average travel distance of travelers

3.1. Developing hierarchical index structure for prioritizing railway development options

Developing hierarchical index structure is the first step for prioritizing railway development options. To achieve this, indices and options defined in previous sections should be placed appropriately in a hierarchical structure. The first level indicates the goal which in our case is prioritizing railway development options.

Factors affecting prioritization are included in the second level. Indices to be considered in our study are competition with the road, demand for each railway option and infrastructure cost for each railway option.

Railway development options are considered in the third level and are divided into three categories: phase 1, 2 and 3. The decision tree has been created by setting the elements in the correct level. **Error! Reference source not found.** illustrates hierarchical decision structure.

Figure 3 hierarchical structure for prioritizing railway development options

3.2. Determination of Ideal and anti-Ideal Criteria

In this study, the problem is solved using the TOPSIS method. Therefore, in this section, effective the criteria are categorized in the ideal groups (parameters which their increase is desirable) and anti-ideal (the parameters for which their decrease is desirable).

Figure 1 Separation of the criteria into Ideal and anti-Ideal groups

3.3. Selected individuals to determine the weight of each indicator

In order to determine the weight of each of the indicators, a total of 23 internal experts were identified and selected during the sessions, and these individuals were identified in the various positions indicated in **Error! Reference source not found.**, and with the dispersion of the level of education From Graduate to Ph.D.

Figure 5 Selected people by position

3.4. Determining the weight of criteria from the point of view of decision makers

In order to determine the weight of the criteria, a design questionnaire was designed and made available to decision makers at Raja Company. By aggregation of decision makers' opinions using the TOPSIS method and normalization, finally, the corresponding values for the weight of each factor were obtained. The values are presented in

Table 2 Weight Values of Criteria

Criteria	Sub-Criteria	Weight
competition with accessible roads	Road Condition	0.22
	The Cost of Road Casualties	0.28
Travel demand	-	0.31
The average cost of construction	-	0.19

3.5. Calculation of the final weight and prioritizing the proposed railway development options

As it was mentioned previously, the method of TOSIS was utilized for ranking of the proposed railway options. Implementation of the method includes 8 stages, the calculation process details of which are not presented here. Only the final step (the model output) which is the calculation of the final weights and ranking of the options are divided into three categories of “phase-1 options”, “phase-2 options” and “phase-3 options” Table 3 to

Table 5.

Table 3 Ranking of “phase 1” options

Ranking	Proposed Railway Line	value
1	Arak - Kermanshah	0.700
2	Saveh - Hamadan - Sanandaj	0.690
3	Sabzevar - Rail	0.432
4	Esfarin - Rail	0.383
5	Mahabad - Maragheh	0.381
6	Mianeh - Bostan Abad	0.357

Table 4 Ranking of “phase 2” options

Ranking	Proposed Railway Line	value
1	Gorgan - Ali Abad-Mashhad	0.746
2	Isfahan - Shahrekord-Ahvaz	0.534
3	Isfahan – Arak	0.531
4	Shiraz - Fasa – Sirjan	0.497
5	Ghaemshahr – Rasht	0.495
6	Zahedan - Birjand – Khaf	0.489
7	Qazvin - Rasht – Astara	0.479
8	Garmsar - Badrud	0.457
9	Shiraz – Bushehr	0.420
10	Kermanshah – Sanandaj	0.408
11	Kashan – Arak	0.379
12	Shiraz - Fasa - Fin (Bandar Abbas)	0.367
13	Ilam - Kermanshah	0.367
14	Kermanshah - Khosravi	0.365
15	Urumieh-Mahabad	0.364
16	Abshour-Mohammadia	0.357
17	Sanandaj – Miandoab	0.353
18	Malayer-Hamedan	0.349
19	Urumieh - Khoy – Maku	0.343
20	Kangwar – Hamadan	0.341
21	Shiraz - Dugenbadan – Mahshahr	0.340
22	Kabodarahang – Takestan	0.340
23	Gorgan - Ali Abad – Shahrood	0.325
24	Segzi – Shahr Reza	0.319
25	Takestan – Saveh	0.317
26	Gorgan – Atrak	0.316
27	Andimeshk – Khorramabad – Nahavand (Arak)	0.308
28	Astara – Ardabil – Mianeh	0.306
29	Hosseinieh – Ilam	0.292
30	Astara - Ardabil – Bostanabad	0.286
31	Sanandaj – Zanjan	0.271
32	Sirjan - Bardsir – Kerman	0.271
33	Bandar Abbas - Kahnouj – Rail	0.254
34	Ghaderabad - Mehriz – Yazd	0.243
35	Chabahar - Iranshahr-Bam	0.225
36	Chabahar - Iranshahr-Zahedan	0.191

Table 5 Ranking of “phase 3” options

Ranking	Proposed Railway Line	value
1	Mahabad – Boukan	0.82
2	Kenartakhteh – Noorabad	0.67
3	Fasa – SaadatShahr	0.64
4	Bojnord – Esfarayen	0.62
5	Mahshahr - Shadegan – Khoramshahr	0.53
6	Boroujerd – Toureh	0.51
7	Takestan - Kuhin	0.49
8	Zanjan – Rudbar	0.46
9	Shahrud – Tabas	0.40
10	Khaf - Torbat Jam - Rails	0.38

4. Conclusions

Since the final purpose of this study was to provide a method for identifying and prioritizing new routes from a passenger perspective, to achieve the goal, the methodology was defined in three sections. First, identifying and defining the routes, then determining the effective indicators on the priority of the options for the development of the railway network and prioritizing the options for the development of the rail with the aim of TOPSIS method and ranking of the routes in the corresponding phases was performed.

In the paths related to phase 1, which is related to the paths under construction, the results of TOPSIS ranking showed that the two routes that are considered to be of high importance from the passenger transportation point of view are:

- Arak - Kermanshah
- Saveh - Hamadan - Sanandaj

Due to the lack of the railway network in the west of the country and high travel demand due to high population density and the inappropriate roads of these areas, the results of the model in the “phase 1” have led to a high ranking of the paths in the west of the country.

“phase 2” options include the majority of the options proposed in this study, and according to the assumptions of the research, their implementation depends to the implementation of the options under construction (“phase 1”), and the construction of these options is in the short and medium term goals of the I.R. Iran Railways. The results of the ranking of the TOPSIS method showed that the three routes which are considered to be in priority from the “passenger transportation” point of view are:

- Gorgan - Ali Abad - Mashhad
- Isfahan – Shahrekord - Ahvaz
- Isfahan - Arak

“phase 3” options are the lines which normally have shorter routes than the main options and are considered as the long-term goals for the railway network development in the I.R. Iran. The results of the ranking of the TOPSIS method showed that the three routes that are considered to have the highest ranking from the “passenger transportation” point of view is:

- Mahabad- Bukan
- KenarTakhteh – Nurabad
- Fasa – SaadatShahr

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